

VALUE project - part 3: SiC and Diamond Sensors for Fast Neutron Spectrum Unfolding in the VENUS-F Reactor

Enrica Belfiore^{1*}, Federico Grimaldi^{2,3}, Federico Di Croce^{2,3}, Antonin Krása², Mehdi Ben Mosbah¹, Rodolphe Antoni¹, Jan Wagemans², Guido Vittiglio²

¹CEA, DES, IRESNE, DTN, Cadarache F-13108, Saint-Paul-Lez-Durance, 13108, France;

²SCK CEN Belgian nuclear research centre, Boeretang 190, Mol, 2400, Belgium;

³Université libre de Bruxelles, Avenue Franklin D. Roosevelt 50, Bruxelles, 1050, Belgium

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804223

ABSTRACT

This work presents a methodology under development at CEA IRESNE for neutron spectrum reconstruction using machine learning algorithms. The proposed approach exploits the energy deposition data recorded by SiC and CVD diamond detectors to reconstruct neutron flux spectrum. A first experimental application was carried out within the VALUE campaign at the VENUS-F zero-power fast reactor. This study reports the first results of the normalized spectra reconstruction performance of SiC and CVD diamond detectors irradiated in the central position of the VENUS-F core assembly. The reconstructed spectra were compared with the calculated neutron flux spectrum of the VENUS-F reactor, and their agreement was quantitatively assessed using the coefficient of determination as a performance metric. The presented findings confirm the capability of the proposed methodology to capture the main features of the fast neutron field of VENUS-F and provide a promising framework for spectrometric diagnostics in advanced reactor systems.

Keywords: Neutron Flux Spectrum Unfolding, Machine Learning, VALUE campaign, VENUS-F reactor, Solid State Detectors

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the neutron flux spectrum within a nuclear reactor is fundamental for both theoretical analyses and experimental investigations. Neutron spectrometry provides essential information for reactor physics studies, fuel behaviour assessments, material irradiation experiments, and safety evaluations [1, 2]. However, measuring the neutron spectrum remains challenging. The neutron field is strongly energy-dependent and spatially heterogeneous, and it varies with reactor design and operating conditions. In addition, practical constraints on detector placement within the core can often further complicate in-core measurements. Consequently, robust detection systems are required to ensure reliable spectral measurements under such conditions. In recent years, solid-state detectors have emerged as promising candidates for neutron spectrometry and flux monitoring in reactor environments. Semiconductor materials such as Silicon Carbide (SiC) and Chemical Vapor Deposited (CVD) diamond crystals have attracted particular interest thanks to their exceptional radiation tolerance, fast response time, low operating voltage, and high energy resolution [3]. Their high atomic displacement threshold energies, ranging from 20 to 35 eV for SiC and 40 to 50 eV for diamond [4], make them significantly more resistant to radiation damage compared to conventional semiconductors such as silicon or germanium. These properties enable their operation in the reactor cores, where other traditional detectors can fail.

At the CEA IRESNE institute in Cadarache, a new methodology is under development for neutron spectrum reconstruction based on machine learning algorithms [5, 6]. This approach leverages the deposited energy data collected by solid-state detectors to reconstruct the neutron flux spectrum where the

*enrica.belfiore@cea.fr

Figure 1. VENUS-F VALUE core lattice. Different colours indicate the materials in the VENUS-F core. Green: 30% w.t. metallic U; yellow: Bi; cyan: Al_2O_3 rodlets; blue: Pb; orange: graphite; gray: structures (mostly stainless steel); red: control rods (visible only in position (-2,-3)). Lattice side length is about 1 m.

deposited energy was measured. Such data-driven methods can overcome the limitations of traditional deconvolution procedures, which often generate oscillatory artefacts and numerical instabilities.

In this work, the performance of the proposed machine learning-based spectrum reconstruction methodology is evaluated and compared for two types of solid detectors: SiC and CVD diamond. The analysis is based on experimental data acquired during the VALUE (VENUS-F Automated Learning Unfolding Experiment) campaign, conducted at the VENUS-F zero-power fast reactor at SCK CEN in Belgium. These preliminary results indicate that solid-state detectors, combined with machine learning, can provide a promising approach for neutron spectrum unfolding in fast reactor environments.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN AT THE VENUS-F REACTOR

The VALUE campaign supported by the OFFERR program of the European Commission, was carried out at the VENUS-F zero-power fast reactor in March 2025. Measurements were performed in the critical VENUS-F core configuration (CC) #14 [7]. CC14 features fuel assemblies with 30% w.t. enriched metallic U, Bi and Al_2O_3 rodlets and Pb plates in a stainless steel casing. The core active region is radially surrounded by Pb and graphite reflector assemblies as well as by an outer Pb reflector. Vertically, the core features a top and bottom lead reflector. Several experimental channels allow for measurement in the active core and in the reflector. Figure 1 shows a view of the VENUS-F configuration used in VALUE. More details on VALUE and characterization measurements of CC14 can be found in the literature [7, 8].

The main objective of VALUE is to reconstruct the neutron spectrum in VENUS-F by combining experimental data from different solid-state detectors with unfolding techniques based on machine learning. Beyond validating the proposed ML-based approach, the campaign is also aimed at benchmarking its performance against conventional unfolding methods. Building up on previous research, the unfolded spectra would not only be compared against calculated spectra in VENUS-F, but also against spectral

indices measured both during VALUE and in previous campaigns [7, 8] with fission chambers and activation foils. This comparison will provide a consistent framework to evaluate both the accuracy and robustness of the machine learning methodology, and to assess its potential as an alternative tool for experimental neutron spectrometry in reactor environments. During VALUE, measurements were conducted in several experimental channels at active core mid-plane. The results for positions (-1,+1), (+3,+3) and (-6,+1) (see Figure 1) are presented in this study for the solid state detectors under analysis. The SiC device features an active area of $1.6 \text{ mm} \times 1.6 \text{ mm}$ with a sensitive layer thickness of $60 \mu\text{m}$. The layer configuration consists of a $1 \mu\text{m}$ aluminium front contact, a $1 \mu\text{m}$ p^+ layer, the active 4H-SiC layer, and a 100 nm titanium–nickel back contact. The CVD diamond detector has an active area of $1.4 \text{ mm} \times 1.4 \text{ mm}$ and a sensitive layer thickness of $320 \mu\text{m}$, with standard metallic contacts consisting of thin gold layers on both sides to ensure good ohmic behavior and signal stability under irradiation. The detectors employed in this study are primarily sensitive to neutrons above approximately 100 keV ; therefore, only this fast portion of the spectrum is considered in the present analysis. Although thermal and epithermal energy ranges can be explored by coupling the detectors with neutron converters such as boron or lithium layers, this aspect is beyond the scope of VALUE.

To fit in the experimental channels considered in this analysis, the detectors were integrated into SMA-type housings with a 9 mm outer maximum diameter. Each detector was connected through a coaxial cable to a custom-built current preamplifier with a gain of 55 dB and a bandwidth of 75 MHz . The bias voltage was supplied by a CAEN DT5533EM high-voltage module, providing -300 V for the SiC detector and -350 V for the CVD diamond detector. The output pulses were digitized using a CAEN DT5743 switched-capacitor digitizer, featuring 8 channels and a sampling rate of 3.2 GHz .

After minimizing the contribution of electronic noise through an appropriate selection of the trigger threshold during data acquisition and a subsequent verification of the signal quality using statistical estimators such as the Fisher–Pearson coefficient of skewness, the recorded waveforms were processed with a dedicated Python-based analysis routine, in order to get the deposited energy as reported in [9].

3. MACHINE LEARNING METHODOLOGY FOR NEUTRON SPECTRUM RECONSTRUCTION

Neutron spectrum reconstruction is performed using a supervised machine learning approach based on Gaussian Process Regression (GPR). The objective of the model is to learn the mapping between the detector response, expressed as deposited energy distributions measured by the solid-state detectors, and the corresponding neutron energy spectra.

The adopted methodology has been previously applied to monoenergetic neutron fields, to broad-spectrum sources such as Am–Be and ^{252}Cf , and to neutron spectra reconstructed in converters inserted in the BR1 reactor cavity [10]. The unfolding procedure is implemented using the `scikit-learn` Python package. Within the supervised learning framework, the training dataset is composed of paired input–output samples. The input features consist of the deposited energy distributions in the detector, while the target outputs are the associated neutron energy spectra, discretized into energy bins.

The training database is based on a library of synthetic neutron spectra generated using analytical functions commonly adopted to reproduce realistic nuclear spectral shapes, such as Watt, Maxwellian, evaporation, Gaussian-like and exponential distributions. The full generation procedure is described in detail in [6].

After applying selection criteria to avoid redundant or non-physical spectra, a total of 544 synthetic neutron spectra were retained and used for training, consistently with previous works [11].

For each retained synthetic neutron spectrum, Monte Carlo simulations of the detector response were performed to generate the corresponding deposited energy distribution. This procedure establishes a one-to-one correspondence between each neutron spectrum and its associated detector response, form-

ing the paired input–output samples used for training the GPR model.

The validation of the algorithm is performed using 121 reference neutron spectra from the IAEA Compendium database [12], which provide a standardized and independent benchmark for performance evaluation.

The unfolding is carried out using Gaussian Process Regression, which models the relationship between the input deposited energy distributions and the output neutron spectra within a probabilistic, non-parametric framework. The GPR predicts, for each energy bin, both the mean value of the reconstructed spectrum and the associated predictive uncertainty, expressed as the posterior variance.

The covariance structure of the model is defined by a composite kernel composed of a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel and a White kernel. The RBF kernel enforces smoothness and continuity in the reconstructed spectra, reflecting the expected physical behavior, while the White kernel accounts for uncorrelated noise arising from statistical fluctuations and measurement variability.

The kernel hyperparameters are optimized during training by maximizing the log-marginal likelihood. The predictive uncertainty returned by the GPR accounts for both intrinsic noise in the training data and the lack of information in sparsely populated regions of the input space, defined here as the feature space spanned by the deposited energy distributions measured in the detector. Higher uncertainties therefore indicate detector response patterns that are under-represented in the training dataset.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the deposited energy (input) for the position (-1, +1) and the reconstructed neutron spectra (output) for the positions (-1, +1), (+3, +3) and (-6, +1) within the VENUS-F reactor obtained with the SiC and CVD diamond detectors. The deposited energy at (-1, +1) is reported as an example of the input to the ML algorithm, while for the other positions the analysis is discussed in [7]. The experimental pulse height spectra, representing the deposited energy distributions, are shown in Figure 2 as histograms and the corresponding continuous lines represent the outcomes of Monte Carlo simulations performed with the PHITS code [13]. The nuclear data used in the simulations were taken from the JENDL-4.0u nuclear data library [14], as it was found to provide the best agreement with experimental results when comparing neutron–carbon interaction cross sections across different evaluated libraries, particularly for alpha-particle production [15, 16]. The experimental uncertainty (counting statistics, assumed to be Poisson distributed) is shown in the error bars as 2σ , whereas the Monte Carlo standard error is represented by the shaded band around the simulated curve. The reconstructed neutron spectra are displayed as step functions divided into 25 energy bins, following the format of the IAEA Compendium benchmark database. The associated uncertainties are reported as error bars corresponding to two standard deviations. All spectra and deposited energy distributions are normalized to their respective integrals.

Figure 2 shows that at low deposited energies (below 1 MeV), where the detector response is primarily attributed to neutron scattering events, the experimental data are in good agreement with the PHITS simulations for both detectors. Minor deviations are observed in the first energy bins, most likely due to partial signal loss induced by noise discrimination, as the acquisition trigger was set to -30 mV. Between 1.3 and 4 MeV, discrepancies between simulated and experimental data become more pronounced. In the case of the SiC detector, these differences arise from reactions involving excited states of ^{25}Mg and ^9Be , as well as from the $^{12}\text{C}(n,n')3\alpha$ reaction channel. These reactions are difficult to model accurately, since the cross section for multiple- α emission is one of the least constrained among carbon–neutron interactions. Significant inconsistencies have been reported among different evaluated nuclear data libraries for these processes [15]. For the CVD diamond detector, the largest deviations between measured and simulated results also originate from multi- α production, mainly visible in the 1–3 MeV deposited energy region. In the SiC detector, the most pronounced differences are found between 3.0 and 3.5 MeV, where calculation-to-experiment discrepancies of up to 40% are observed when using the

Figure 2. Deposited energy in SiC and CVD diamond detectors irradiated in (-1,+1) location of the VENUS-F assembly.

Figure 3. Top row: Machine-Learning reconstructed neutron spectra from the SiC (red) and CVD diamond (blue) detectors data in position (a) (-1, +1), (b) (+3, +3) and (c) (-6, +1) of the VENUS-F core assembly. Bottom row: R^2 values per bin comparing each reconstructed energy bin with the reference simulated spectrum.

JENDL-4.0u data. Above 3.3 MeV, the simulations fall within 2σ of the experimental values. In this region, the deposited energy in SiC is dominated by the $^{28}\text{Si}(n, p)^{28}\text{Al}$ reaction, which is generally better characterized than the multi- α emission channels, with only a minor contribution from α -particle production. The discrepancies observed between the simulated and measured deposited-energy distributions directly propagate into the reconstructed neutron spectra shown in the upper part of Figure 3. Since the unfolding relies on detector response functions derived from simulations, any mismatch in the deposited-energy domain influences the spectral reconstruction. The Gaussian Process Regressor used in this work provides an associated uncertainty estimate, which reflects both the quality of the training data and the level of agreement between simulations and measurements. As a result, larger

deviations between simulated and measured deposited-energy distributions manifest as increased predictive uncertainty in the reconstructed spectra. The reconstruction of each energy bin is compared with the reference simulated spectrum using the coefficient of determination (R^2), with the resulting values presented in the bottom part of Figure 3. As expected, moving from the central region toward the outer core, the neutron spectrum becomes increasingly thermalized, resulting in a reduced fast-neutron component.

For all positions, the energy region dominated by elastic scattering—approximately up to 2 MeV—is accurately reproduced. This behaviour is consistent with the fact that elastic interactions are well characterized in the evaluated nuclear data libraries used for training the model. Above 2 MeV, additional reaction channels begin to contribute significantly, most notably carbon inelastic scattering and the $^{28}\text{Si}(n, \alpha)^{25}\text{Mg}$ reaction. Inelastic scattering on carbon can generate multiple α -particles, a process not explicitly represented in the simulations employed to build the training database for spectrum unfolding. Consequently, the reconstruction performance in this region largely depends on the relative abundance of neutrons above 2 MeV.

- **Position (−1, +1):** As shown in Figure 3a, this location presents the highest flux of neutrons above 2 MeV among the three investigated positions. As a result, multi- α production in carbon is more pronounced, leading to a less accurate reconstruction between 2 and 4 MeV. Within this interval, the SiC detector shows a slightly closer agreement with the reference spectrum compared with the CVD diamond detector, although the low number of high-energy bins prevents drawing firm conclusions. This marginal improvement may be attributed to the $^{28}\text{Si}(n, \alpha)^{25}\text{Mg}$ contribution in the SiC detector, which partly compensates for the multi- α production in carbon, as the corresponding cross sections are of comparable magnitude. The largest deviations from the simulated spectrum occur above 6 MeV, where α -particle production becomes increasingly dominant for both detectors, leading to larger uncertainties in the reconstructed flux. This trend is reflected in the monotonic decrease of the bin-wise R^2 values shown in Figure 3, which indicates the growing difficulty in accurately reconstructing higher-energy bins dominated by less well-characterized reaction channels. The overall R^2 , computed as the average of the bin-wise values, is 0.85 for the SiC detector and 0.81 for the CVD diamond detector. Although these values suggest good agreement over the full energy range, they are strongly influenced by the larger number of bins below 2 MeV where reconstruction performance is optimal. Therefore, the averaged R^2 does not fully capture the reduced accuracy at high energies and should be interpreted with caution. A figure of merit less sensitive to the binning strategy will be explored in future work.
- **Position (+3, +3):** The reconstruction at this position (Figure 3b) exhibits a similar qualitative behaviour to (−1, +1). However, the bin-wise R^2 values at higher energies are slightly improved compared with the (−1, +1) case, most likely due to the lower flux of neutrons above 2 MeV and, consequently, the reduced impact of α -particle production mechanisms. This reduction in high-energy neutron content mitigates the contribution of reaction channels that are not fully represented in the training database, producing a modest improvement in reconstruction fidelity at higher energies.
- **Position (−6, +1):** At the most peripheral location (Figure 3c), the reconstructed spectrum shows the best overall agreement with the simulated reference. This improvement is primarily driven by the much lower fast-neutron content, which minimizes the contribution of α -particle-producing reactions and thereby reduces the mismatch with respect to the training database. Notably, the first two energy bins display a slightly higher R^2 compared with the corresponding bins at the other positions. This is attributable to an improved experimental configuration during those measurements: a new signal cable and a reduced noise level were employed, enabling a lower trigger threshold and the collection of deposited energies closer to the lower detection limit. The lowered threshold enhanced the detector sensitivity in the lowest-energy bins and thus improved the reconstruction quality in that range. While beneficial, these experimental differences introduce a

small systematic offset in the low-energy response that is not yet modeled in the current unfolding procedure. Overall, the results at $(-6, +1)$ indicate that, in spectral regions dominated by well-characterized interactions and minimal competing reaction channels, the GPR approach is capable of achieving highly accurate spectrum reconstructions.

However, the adopted 25-bin energy grid is considered insufficient for accurately representing the VENUS-F neutron spectrum, as it fails to capture several of its characteristic spectral structures. For this reason, future analyses will employ a finer energy discretization, requiring an updated database for the machine-learning workflow. In parallel, a deep-learning framework based on Bayesian neural networks is currently being investigated to further improve the reconstruction capabilities.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a selection of preliminary results obtained with SiC and CVD diamond detectors during the experimental campaign carried out within the VALUE project. In particular, the analysis focused on the sensors irradiated in the positions $(-1, +1)$, $(+3, +3)$ and $(-6, +1)$ of the VENUS-F core, comparing the measured deposited-energy distributions with PHITS simulations performed using nuclear data from the JENDL-4.0u library. The results indicate that elastic scattering reactions are well reproduced for both silicon and carbon nuclei, while the largest discrepancies arise from multi- α particle production. The deposited-energy data were used as input for the Gaussian process-based machine learning model, which reconstructs the neutron spectrum in 25 energy bins. Each reconstructed bin was compared with the reference simulated spectrum through the R^2 metric, showing that the discrepancies observed in the deposited energy are reflected in the reconstructed spectra. The SiC-based reconstruction exhibits slightly better agreement in the inelastic scattering region. This improved behaviour may be related to differences in the response functions included in the training database, particularly the presence of silicon reaction channels, although a detailed analysis of their individual contributions is beyond the scope of the present analysis. The overall R^2 , obtained as the average across all energy bins, exceeds 0.80 for both detectors and locations, indicating a promising agreement with the reference neutron spectrum and demonstrating the potential of combining solid-state detectors with machine learning for neutron spectrometry applications. Future work will aim at improving the reconstruction fidelity by increasing the number of energy bins and extending the analysis toward deep-learning approaches. Additional measurements in other positions of the VENUS-F assembly, along with comparisons against alternative unfolding techniques, will further support the comprehensive validation of the proposed methodology.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported financially by Association Vinçotte Nuclear (AVN), ENEN2Plus project and by the Horizon Europe programme through the OFFERR project (101060008).

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Cao, Q. Gan, J. Song, P. Long, B. Wu, and Y. Wu. "A two-step neutron spectrum unfolding method for fission reactors based on artificial neural network." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 139 (2020).
- [2] M. Drissi El-Bouzaidi, T. El Bardouni, E. Chham, O. El Hajjaji, A. Nouayti, A. Idrissi, and K. El-Bakkari. "Unfolding of the neutron spectrum in a nuclear reactor using genetic algorithms method." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, volume 422 (2024).
- [3] O. Obraztsova, L. Ottaviani, A. Klix, T. Döring, O. Palais, and A. Lyoussi. "Comparison between Silicon-Carbide and diamond for fast neutron detection at room temperature." *EPJ Web Conf*, vol-

ume 170 (2018).

- [4] G. Lucas and L. Pizzagalli. "Comparison of threshold displacement energies in β -SiC determined by classical potentials and ab initio calculations." *Nucl Instrum Methods Phys Res B*, volume 229(3) (2005).
- [5] R. Antoni, P.-G. Allineï, and L. Bourgois. "Prediction of fast neutron spectra with a spherical TEPC using a machine-learning algorithm." *Nucl Instrum Methods Phys Res A*, volume 1050 (2023).
- [6] E. Belfiore, R. Antoni, M. Ben Mosbah, P.-G. Allineï, D. Tisseur, O. Llido, and J.-E. Groetz. "Theoretical analysis of neutron spectra measurement with SiC detectors using a machine learning technique." *Journal of Instrumentation*, volume 19(10) (2024).
- [7] F. Grimaldi, E. Belfiore, F. D. Croce, A. Krása, M. B. Mosbah, P. Blaise, P.-E. Labeau, J. Wagemans, and G. Vittiglio. "Measurements of $^{232}\text{Th}/^{235}\text{U}$, $^{238}\text{U}/^{235}\text{U}$ Fission Rate Ratios and Deposited Energy in SiC and Diamond Detectors from the VALUE Campaign at VENUS-F." *submitted to IEEE TNS special ANIMMA 2025 issue*.
- [8] F. Grimaldi, F. Di Croce, A. Krása, G. de Izarra, L. Barbot, P. Blaise, P.-E. Labeau, L. Fiorito, G. Vittiglio, and J. Wagemans. "The CoRREx neutron spectrum filtering campaign at VENUS-F for calculation-to-experiment discrepancy interpretation." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 219 (2025).
- [9] Q. Potiron, C. Destouches, L. Dubus, M. Houry, O. Llido, A. Lyoussi, L. Ottaviani, and C. Reynard-Carette. "Modelling of a SiC Based Detector for the Interpretation of 14.1 MeV Neutrons Measurements." *EPJ Web Conf*, volume 288 (2023).
- [10] E. Belfiore, F. Grimaldi, F. D. Croce, A. Krása, M. B. Mosbah, R. Antoni, J. Wagemans, G. Vittiglio, A. Lyoussi, and J.-E. Groetz. "Machine Learning-Based Unfolding of Neutron Spectra in the BR1 Research Reactor Cavity Using 4H-SiC Solid State Detectors." *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science* (2026).
- [11] E. Belfiore, P.-G. Allineï, P. Houedry, M. Bahhi, S. Bartolacci, A. Saleh, M. Ben Mosbah, R. Antoni, A. Lyoussi, and J.-E. Groetz. "Comparative assessment of feature extraction for fast neutron spectra prediction with machine learning algorithms using a CVD diamond detector." *Nucl Instrum Methods Phys Res A*, volume 1082 (2026).
- [12] *Compendium of Neutron Spectra and Detector Responses for Radiation Protection Purposes*. Number 318 in Technical Reports Series. INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Vienna (1990).
- [13] T. Sato, K. Niita, N. Matsuda, S. Hashimoto, Y. Iwamoto, T. Furuta, S. Noda, T. Ogawa, H. Iwase, H. Nakashima, T. Fukahori, K. Okumura, T. Kai, S. Chiba, and L. Sihver. "Overview of particle and heavy ion transport code system PHITS." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 82 (2015).
- [14] K. Shibata, O. Iwamoto, T. Nakagawa, N. Iwamoto, A. Ichihara, S. Kunieda, S. Chiba, K. Furutaka, N. Otuka, T. Ohsawa, T. Murata, H. Matsunobu, A. Zukeran, S. Kamada, and J. ichi Katakura. "JENDL-4.0: A New Library for Nuclear Science and Engineering." *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, volume 48(1) (2011).
- [15] E. Belfiore, M. Ben Mosbah, and R. Antoni. "Cross Section Discrepancies in Neutron-Carbon Interactions at 14 MeV: a Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis." *International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2025)*.
- [16] E. Belfiore, A. Chalil, M. Ben Mosbah, R. Antoni, O. Llido, A. Lyoussi, C. Destouches, T. Slavicek, A. Šagátová, and J.-E. Groetz. "Reconstruction of Neutron Spectra Using Silicon Carbide Detectors in Monoenergetic Fields with Machine Learning Approach." *EPJ Web Conf*, volume 338 (2025).